

Intuitionistic deductive tableaux

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Abstract

We present a deductive method for propositional intuitionistic logic based on tableaux. We prove its soundness and completeness based on given semantical definitions. The classical case is considered as slight variations of the intuitionistic case.

We present here a method for logical deductions for propositional intuitionistic logic called *deductive tableaux*. It can be seen as a generalisation of the familiar analytic tableaux method (c.f. Smullyan [5]) so as to include also synthetic (and conditional) rules, in order to allow the construction of intuitionistic deductions in a direct fashion. Deductions are then presented as a special case of what we call, following Kneale ([4] ch. IX.3), a logical *development* of the premisses. For, in particular, the rule for analysing disjunctions is not a deduction rule, as in natural deduction systems, but a rule allowing one to expand the cases considered in the search of the conclusion. In this way we achieve a nicer symmetry and duality for the rules of conjunction and disjunction.¹

In the next section, we offer the basic linguistic and semantical definitions. The semantics is defined as a sort of ‘inexact truth-maker semantics’, which amounts to a slight reformulation of the more usual possible-world semantics, the notion of worlds being replaced by a notion of a state of things. Next, in section 2, we present the definitions and rules of developments. We consider in each case also how classical logic might be obtained as slight variations of the intuitionistic case. Finally, in sections 3 and (forthcoming) 5 we argue respectively for the soundness and completeness of this method.

1 Language and semantics

The propositional language we will consider consists of the logical connectives for *conjunction*, *disjunction*, *implication* and *negation*, i.e. \wedge , \vee , \rightarrow and \neg , respectively, used to form molecular formulas from the *atomic formulas* (i.e. *propositional variables*) $p, q, r \dots$ in the usual way. We will use $\varphi, \psi, \chi \dots$ as metavariables for formulas.

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¹In the classical case, this method is in fact identical to the ‘deduction trees’ presented by Jeffrey in [3]. But he doesn’t consider any form of generalisation so as to include implication as primitive and characterize intuitionistic logic as we do here.

The semantics for this language will be constructed considering the notion of a *state* of things verifying a statement. A notion of *proposition* is then given as a set of states, intuitively thought of as the states that verify such proposition. This semantics is based on one presented by Fine in [2] and adapted following ideas of Batchelor in [1].

By an *elementary situation space* (e.s.s.) we will mean simply a set, whose elements we will call *elementary situations*.

A *state* is then defined as a set of elementary situations (i.e. a subset of some e.s.s.). Notice then that the states concerning some e.s.s. are partially ordered by the inclusion relation \subseteq on sets. We will use $\Sigma, \Sigma', \Sigma''$ etc. to denote states.

A *proposition* is defined now as a set of states (i.e. a subset of the power set of some e.s.s.).

Finally, a *model* is defined as a pair (S, σ) , where S is an e.s.s. and σ is a function assigning a proposition (over S) to each propositional variable. This assigning function σ must satisfy the following *hereditary condition* (HC):

$$\Sigma \in \sigma(p) \Rightarrow \forall \Sigma' (\Sigma \subseteq \Sigma' \Rightarrow \Sigma' \in \sigma(p)) \quad (1)$$

Put simply, this condition imposes that if some state verifies p then every superstate (i.e. superset) of it also does. I.e. every proposition assigned to atoms must be closed under superstates.

The following clauses then extend σ to all formulas:

$$\sigma(\varphi \wedge \psi) = \{\Sigma \cup \Sigma' : \Sigma \in \sigma(\varphi) \text{ and } \Sigma' \in \sigma(\psi)\} \quad (2)$$

$$\sigma(\varphi \vee \psi) = \sigma(\varphi) \cup \sigma(\psi) \quad (3)$$

$$\sigma(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) = \{\Sigma : \forall \Sigma' \supseteq \Sigma, \Sigma' \in \sigma(\varphi) \Rightarrow \Sigma' \in \sigma(\psi)\} \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma(\neg\varphi) = \{\Sigma : \forall \Sigma' \supseteq \Sigma, \Sigma' \notin \sigma(\varphi)\} \quad (5)$$

Proposition 1.1. *HC is satisfied by the extended σ .*

Considering a set Γ of formulas, we define $\sigma(\Gamma)$ as the set of states that verify simultaneously all formulas in Γ . I.e. $\sigma(\Gamma) = \bigcap \{\sigma(\varphi) : \forall \varphi \in \Gamma\}$. But we will also have $\sigma(\emptyset) = \wp(S)$, i.e. any state verify no formula at all.

We now can define what it means for a formula φ to be a *intuitionistic consequence* of a set of formulas Γ – in symbols, $\Gamma \vDash \varphi$:

$$\Gamma \vDash \varphi \quad =_{\text{def}} \quad \forall \text{ model } (S, \sigma) : \sigma(\Gamma) \subseteq \sigma(\varphi) \quad (6)$$

I.e. φ is a consequence of Γ if and only if for any model every state verifying Γ also verifies φ . And we can define *intuitionistic validity* of some formula φ – i.e. $\vDash \varphi$ – as consequence from the empty set of formulas, so that any valid formula is verified by every state in every model. (In particular, any valid formula is verified by the empty state, so that by the hereditary condition it will be verified by every state.)

Conjecture 1.2. (Classical models) *Dropping the hereditary condition on σ and restating its extension clauses as follows defines a notion of a classical model (S, σ) , with everything else defined as before²:*

$$\sigma(\varphi \wedge \psi) = \sigma(\varphi) \cap \sigma(\psi) \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma(\varphi \vee \psi) = \sigma(\varphi) \cup \sigma(\psi) \quad (8)$$

$$\sigma(\varphi \rightarrow \psi) = \{\Sigma : \Sigma \in \sigma(\varphi) \Rightarrow \Sigma \in \sigma(\psi)\} \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma(\neg\varphi) = \{\Sigma : \Sigma \notin \sigma(\varphi)\} \quad (10)$$

2 Intuitionistic developments

A *development* of Γ is any tableau initiated by the formulas in Γ in a single branch and then extended only according to the rules below:

$$\begin{array}{c}
 \downarrow \wedge^{(i)} \frac{\varphi \wedge \psi}{\varphi} \quad \downarrow \wedge^{(ii)} \frac{\varphi \wedge \psi}{\psi} \\
 \\
 \downarrow \vee \frac{\varphi \vee \psi}{\varphi \mid \psi} \\
 \\
 \downarrow \rightarrow \frac{\varphi \rightarrow \psi, \varphi}{\psi} \\
 \\
 \downarrow \neg \frac{\neg\varphi, \varphi}{\psi}
 \end{array}
 \left|
 \begin{array}{c}
 \uparrow \wedge \frac{\varphi, \psi}{\varphi \wedge \psi} \\
 \\
 \uparrow \vee^{(i)} \frac{\varphi}{\varphi \vee \psi} \quad \uparrow \vee^{(ii)} \frac{\psi}{\varphi \vee \psi} \\
 \\
 \uparrow \rightarrow \frac{\boxed{\varphi \dots \psi}}{\varphi \rightarrow \psi} \\
 \\
 \uparrow \neg \frac{\boxed{\varphi \dots \neg\varphi}}{\neg\varphi}
 \end{array}
 \right.$$

In these rules, formulas separated by a comma belong to the same branch. $\varphi \mid \psi$ in the conclusion of a rule means branching with φ on the left and ψ on the right.

The expressions of the form $\boxed{\varphi \dots \psi}$ indicate a deduction (see definition below) of ψ from the additional assumption φ (and anything occurring asserted in the same branch above φ). The calculus has then a single structural rule \mathfrak{W} (for *Weakening*) which allows the introduction of an additional assumption inside a *conditional context*, i.e. a box, at any point in a development:

$$\mathfrak{W} \frac{}{\boxed{\varphi}}$$

²But note that now it is not required for the states to have mereological properties amongst themselves. We could then have just a simple set of states in the model definition, with no mention of elementary situations. This is also possible in the intuitionistic case (being in fact the more usual approach), provided we add to the model definition a partial order on the set of states (and redefine the clauses in terms of this relation instead of inclusion). This approach is more general in some aspects, in particular for it allows models with countably many states. In the approach we adopted above, all models will have either finitely many states or uncountably many, according as the e.s.s. is finite or infinite.

The rules $\uparrow\rightarrow$ and $\uparrow\neg$ then allow the introduction of the conclusion outside a box of the corresponding form. A conditional box, consisting itself of a development, occupies then a single point in the outer development branch.

Formulas occurring inside a conditional context are said to be *assumed* relatively to formulas occurring outside. These, in turn, are said to be *asserted* relatively to those occurring inside. A formula occurring outside any conditional box is said to be *affirmed* in it's branch. A development then is said to affirm some formula if it is affirmed in every branch. Now, for Γ a finite set of formulas, we define:

- A *deduction* of formula φ from Γ ($\Gamma \vdash \varphi$) $=_{\text{def}}$ a development of Γ that affirms φ .
- A *proof* of φ ($\vdash \varphi$) $=_{\text{def}}$ a deduction of φ from \emptyset . (I.e. a development that starts from the single empty branch, proceeds necessarily with applications of \mathfrak{W} and, at some point, necessarily uses $\uparrow\rightarrow$ or $\uparrow\neg$)
- A *refutation* of Γ ($\Gamma \vdash \neg$) $=_{\text{def}}$ a deduction of $\neg\varphi$ for some $\varphi \in \Gamma$.

Proposition 2.1. (Classical calculus) *Redefining $\uparrow\rightarrow$ and $\uparrow\neg$ as follows and dropping \mathfrak{W} (i.e. dropping all the conditional apparatus) results in a system of classical logic:*

$$\uparrow\rightarrow^{(i)} \frac{}{\varphi \rightarrow \psi \mid \varphi} \quad \uparrow\rightarrow^{(ii)} \frac{\psi}{\varphi \rightarrow \psi} \quad \uparrow\neg \frac{}{\neg\varphi \mid \varphi}$$

Alternatively, it is possible to maintain all the intuitionistic rules and just add either one of the following:

$$RA \frac{\boxed{\neg\varphi \dots \varphi}}{\varphi} \quad \downarrow\neg\neg \frac{}{\neg\neg\varphi}$$

3 Soundness

We will now prove that our intuitionistic deductive calculus above is sound, i.e. that if $\Gamma \vdash \varphi$ then $\Gamma \models \varphi$. First we prove the following proposition, which states that in a development of Γ , ‘ Γ -consequence’ is preserved in at least one branch.

Proposition 3.1. *Let $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_n$ be the branches of some development of Γ . Then for at least one θ_i ($1 \leq i \leq n$), $\forall \varphi \in \theta_i \Gamma \models \varphi$.*

Proof. Note first that any development of Γ is some extension of the tableau \mathfrak{T} consisting only of the formulas in Γ in a single branch θ . Clearly $\Gamma \models \varphi \forall \varphi \in \theta$ (since $\theta = \Gamma$). So now we will show that if the lemma is true for some arbitrary development \mathfrak{T}' of Γ and branch θ' , then it is also true for any immediate extension of θ' by one of the eight rules above. We consider then the possible application of each rule to θ' :

1. We apply $\downarrow\wedge$, so that some $\varphi \wedge \psi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \varphi \wedge \psi$. Any state Σ that verify $\varphi \wedge \psi$ is a superstate of the states that verify φ and ψ , so that, by HC, $\Sigma \in \sigma(\varphi)$ and $\Sigma \in \sigma(\psi)$. So $\Gamma \models \varphi$ and $\Gamma \models \psi$.
2. We apply $\uparrow\wedge$, so that some $\varphi, \psi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \varphi$ and $\Gamma \models \psi$. So $\sigma(\Gamma) \subseteq \sigma(\varphi) \cap \sigma(\psi)$, which, by HC, is equal to $\sigma(\varphi \wedge \psi)$. Therefore $\Gamma \models \varphi \wedge \psi$.
3. We apply $\downarrow\vee$, so that some $\varphi \vee \psi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \varphi \vee \psi$. Then it is clear by the clause for \vee that $\Gamma \models \varphi$ or $\Gamma \models \psi$.
4. We apply $\uparrow\vee$, so that either $\varphi \in \theta'$ or $\psi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \varphi$ or $\Gamma \models \psi$. Then it is clear that $\Gamma \models \varphi \vee \psi$.
5. We apply $\downarrow\rightarrow$, so that some $\varphi \rightarrow \psi, \varphi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \varphi \rightarrow \psi$ and $\Gamma \models \varphi$. So every state that verify Γ is a state that verify φ and also $\varphi \rightarrow \psi$. So, by the clause for \rightarrow , every such state also verify ψ and then $\Gamma \models \psi$.
6. We apply $\uparrow\rightarrow$, so that some $\boxed{\varphi \dots \psi} \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\} \models \psi$. Obviously also $\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\} \models \varphi$. So, for every model, $\sigma(\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\}) \subseteq \sigma(\varphi) \cap \sigma(\psi) \subseteq \sigma(\varphi \rightarrow \psi)$. Which means $\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\} \models \varphi \rightarrow \psi$. Any state in $\sigma(\Gamma)$ not in $\sigma(\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\})$ is then a state not in $\sigma(\varphi)$ and for which we know that every superstate which is in $\sigma(\varphi)$ is also in $\sigma(\psi)$. This means every such state is in $\sigma(\varphi \rightarrow \psi)$. And so $\Gamma \models \varphi \rightarrow \psi$.
7. We apply $\downarrow\neg$, so that some $\neg\varphi, \varphi \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \models \neg\varphi$ and $\Gamma \models \varphi$. So, for every model, $\sigma(\Gamma) = \emptyset$, for clearly $\sigma(\varphi) \cap \sigma(\neg\varphi) = \emptyset$ by the clause for \neg . Therefore $\Gamma \models \psi$ for any ψ .
8. We apply $\uparrow\neg$, so that some $\boxed{\varphi \dots \neg\varphi} \in \theta'$:
By hypothesis then $\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\} \models \neg\varphi$. But also $\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\} \models \varphi$. Which means $\sigma(\Gamma \cup \{\varphi\}) = \emptyset$ for every model, i.e. no state verify simultaneously Γ and φ . This then means that $\sigma(\Gamma) \subseteq \sigma(\neg\varphi)$ for every model, i.e. $\Gamma \models \neg\varphi$.

■

Theorem 3.2. (Soundness) $\Gamma \vdash \varphi \Rightarrow \Gamma \models \varphi$.

Proof. Assume the hypothesis. This means there exists a development of Γ that affirms φ (i.e. with φ in every branch). By the previous proposition then $\Gamma \models \varphi$. ■

References

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